

ISSN(E): 2770-8125

EUROPEAN INTERNATIONAL
JOURNAL OF ADVANCED
RESEARCH AND INNOVATIONS

EIJARI

2026

www.innojournals.my.id/index.php/eijari

European International Journal of Advanced Research and Innovations

Volume 02, Issue 05

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USE OF MOBILE ROBOTS IN AUTOMATING WAREHOUSE OPERATIONS FOR PRODUCT STORAGE

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Abstract. This article discusses the development of a robotic system utilizing mobile wheeled robots for automating the operation of product storage warehouses. The study describes the architecture of the robotic complex and presents algorithms that characterize the operational principles of the system.

Keywords: automation, mobile robot, control algorithm, route, warehouse.

Introduction. In the modern era of rapid technological advancement, the automation of technological processes is increasingly being integrated into various industrial sectors. One of the areas with significant automation potential is warehouse management, where efficient interaction between technological processes within storage facilities plays a crucial role.

Literature Review and Methodology. One of the approaches to warehouse automation is the development of a robotic complex designed to automate warehouse operations. Such operations include loading, transportation within the warehouse area, unloading of goods, and optimized placement of products on warehouse racks. The main components ensuring the efficient operation of the system include:

1. **Wheeled mobile robots** with high load-carrying capacity equipped with manipulators. These robots perform repetitive mechanical tasks traditionally carried out by warehouse personnel, such as loading, unloading, transporting goods from storage locations to loading zones and back, as well as moving goods throughout the warehouse area.

2. A **control system** responsible for coordinating the interaction between mobile robots, assigning tasks, and optimizing additional logistics processes within the warehouse environment.

a) Rack-moving robot. b) Unit-load transport robot. c) Cargo placement robot.

Figure 1. Mobile robots [1].

The operational principle of the system can be explained through the following typical interaction algorithm between system components:

1. The control system receives information about the necessity of loading cargo X at a specified time.
2. The control system analyzes information about the cargo and determines the storage rack where it is located.
3. Considering the current positions of other robots, the control system generates an optimal route for an available mobile robot while preventing traffic congestion and collisions at route intersections.
4. The transport robot receives a command to move along the assigned route.
5. The mobile robot identifies, grasps, and delivers the cargo to the loading area.

The implementation of such a robotic complex can reduce the number of warehouse personnel by approximately 95%, minimize the influence of human factors, decrease the probability of operational errors, and significantly increase warehouse throughput.

Figure 2. Block diagram of the motion algorithm.

During the development of such systems, particular importance is given to determining optimal movement routes and coordinating the interaction between mobile robots. The efficiency of these processes directly affects system performance

indicators, such as warehouse throughput and the number of collisions between robot routes.

To ensure the execution of tasks assigned to the mobile robot, specialized motion control algorithms were developed. Functionally, these algorithms can be divided into two categories. Within the scope of this study, the global algorithm is considered. This algorithm provides optimal route selection and trajectory tracking.

When no task is assigned, the robot remains in standby mode. At the same time, information regarding the robot's heading angle and current position is stored in memory. Additionally, two data matrices are maintained in the system memory:

1. Adjacency matrix, containing information about connections between nodes and their corresponding weights (distances between points).
2. Coordinate matrix, containing the x, y coordinates of all points in the workspace plane [2].

An example of a graph representation consists of nodes corresponding to target points (intersections within the warehouse) and edges representing corridors connecting these points.

Figure 3. Adjacency matrix and its corresponding graph.

When a command is received to move to a specified point, the function for calculating the optimal path sequence is activated. This function is based on the shortest path search algorithm in a weighted graph — the Dijkstra algorithm. The input data for the function include the adjacency matrix, starting coordinates, and destination coordinates. The output is a sequence of points through which the robot reaches the specified target.

During initialization, the label of the starting node *aaa* is assigned a value of zero, while all other nodes are assigned infinity, indicating that distances from the starting node are initially unknown. All graph nodes are marked as unvisited.

At each step of the algorithm, if all nodes have been visited, the algorithm terminates. Otherwise, among the unvisited nodes, the node uuu with the minimum label value is selected. All possible paths through node uuu are examined. Neighboring nodes connected through edges originating from uuu are analyzed. For each unvisited neighbor, a new path length is calculated as the sum of the current label of uuu and the edge length between uuu and the neighbor. If the resulting value is smaller than the neighbor's current label, the label is updated. After all neighbors are processed, node uuu is marked as visited, and the procedure repeats [3].

For example, in the considered graph, the result of moving from node 1 to node 5 may produce the following sequence: 1 – 2 – 3 – 5.

For each obtained point, the following motion algorithm is sequentially executed:

1. Calculation of the deviation angle of the vector connecting the current and next points relative to the Ox axis.
2. Formation of the turning angle value based on the current course angle and the required angle.
3. Execution of the turning function and updating of the new course angle.
4. Execution of straight-line movement.

Upon reaching the final destination, the robot switches back to standby mode.

Testing and comparison of the developed algorithm with existing analogs demonstrated that representing the environment as a simplified weighted graph significantly reduces computational resource consumption. This improves computational efficiency and positively affects the economic feasibility of the project.

Another important issue is the selection of a method for determining robot position coordinates. One of the most common approaches involves the use of odometric sensors for calculating the distance traveled by each wheel, thereby enabling estimation of the robot's relative position. Typical examples include photoelectric incremental rotary encoders mounted on the output shafts of motors or gearboxes. However, the disadvantage of this method is the accumulation of positioning errors caused by wheel slippage under real operating conditions [4].

Results. The conducted research demonstrated that the route calculation algorithm based on a warehouse layout, combined with incremental encoders having a resolution of 150 arcseconds, results in an accumulated positioning error of approximately 25 cm after one hour of continuous operation.

Therefore, in order to reduce accumulated errors, the use of additional positioning correction methods is proposed. These include ceiling-mounted or floor-mounted sensors placed at specific checkpoints, where the accumulated error can be reset to zero when the robot passes through them.

Conclusion. Based on the conducted research, it can be concluded that the developed algorithm is universal and can be applied to almost any industrial process with only minor modifications. Furthermore, the combined use of odometric sensors and additional error-reset systems ensures high operational accuracy, making the

proposed system suitable for applications involving critical processes where large positioning errors are unacceptable.

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